

PROCESS ASPECTS OF FORMING POLYETHYLENE-BASED COMPOSITES FILLED WITH FUNCTIONAL WASTE-PLANT FILLERS BY ROTATIONAL MOLDING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

This study compares the impact of a one- or two-stage manufacturing processing procedure of high-density polyethylene-based (HDPE) composites filled with ground pistachio (PS), pecan (PES) shells (2-15 wt%) on the rheological, mechanical properties, and the structure of rotomolded products. The investigations were supplemented with an analysis of changes in the resistance of polyethylene composites to oxidation induced by the migration of low molecular weight compounds with antioxidant activity from plant-based fillers to HDPE matrix.

1. Introduction

Rotational molding (RM) technology is currently the most dynamically developing technology for manufacturing thin-walled and large-sized products made of thermoplastic polymers. It involves (i) introducing into a mold, reflecting the external shape of the product, a thermoplastic polymer in the form of powder with defined granulometric characteristics [1]; (ii) putting it in motion in two axes while simultaneously supplying the heat necessary to sinter the polymer and next melting it, guaranteeing the coverage of all walls of the mold; (iii) the subsequent slow cooling and demolding [2–4]. One of the major problems of RM is the long forming time and the resulting energy consumption. Therefore, new solutions for improving its sustainability are sought.

As in the case of other technologies, many attempts have been made to produce polymer composites in RM. The main goal is to change its thermal properties [5] or improve its mechanical properties by introducing fibers [6,7]. Due to the non-pressure nature of the process and the lack of the impact of shear forces during melting, the use of fillers is often associated with their inhomogeneous distribution in product, agglomeration, or porosity of the final rotomolded composite parts [8,9].

During the forming of polymer composites in the rotational molding process, technological problems are encountered as limitations related to passive participation in the initial stage of the molding process,

i.e., the sintering process, as well as difficult degassing of the product caused by increased viscosity from bulk and residual moisture in the filler resulting in additional porosity.

Several methods have been reported in the literature to improve the quality and properties of products, including the use of additional melt processing to obtain a composite micro powder containing filler particles saturated by the polymeric matrix [10], performing the process in multiple stages to get a layered structure of the composite, including with an increased share filler in the internal layers [11,12] or the use of an additional pressurization step, which increases the degree of suction of the filler by the polymer, increases the efficiency and shortens the time of the densification process [13,14].

The development of new sustainable material solutions in the processing of thermoplastic polymers concerns both the application of biopolymers and the use of valorized plant derivatives as fillers and modifiers of petrochemical polymers [15]. The dominant global share of polyethylene in RM is making plant-originated fillers a more frequently used solution. At the same time, after many years of research, they are not only considered materials that make the product cheaper by reducing the amount of polymer but also consciously use new functional features resulting from their complex chemical composition. Considering the fragile nature and low thermal stability of organic compounds having functional features, including antioxidant effects, it is advisable to undertake research not only to determine the final properties of the composites containing them but also to describe the degradation accompanying the processing qualitatively. At the same time, due to the harsh processing environment in rotomolding technology resulting in the need for polymer stabilization, using functional fillers enabling the production of self-stabilizing wood-polymer composites requires combining the analysis of the structure-property relationship with a simultaneous comprehensive analysis of processing and active compounds passivation effects [16].

Taking into account the beneficial role of the slip agent during RM described in [17] and the possibility of the active impact of phytochemicals contained in fillers of plant origin [18,19], attempts were made in this study to verify the possibility of using nut shells as fillers. These fillers were used to achieve a simultaneous effect, plasticization, and stabilization of polyethylene due to the migration of oils rich in antioxidants from nut shells to the polyethylene matrix. The work also refers to the influence of the filler introduction procedure, i.e., using one- or two-step processing.

2.1. Experimental

2.1.1. Materials

The polymer used as a matrix to produce rotomolded composites was the high-density polyethylene (HDPE) KT 10000 UE (Dow, USA), with a melt flow index (MFI) of 8.0 g/10 min (190°C; 2.16 kg), 0.964 g/cm³ density. Pistachio nut shells (PS) were obtained mechanically by manually cracking the nuts from the NATURAL EXPERT PPH Kamil Chojnowski (Poland). Pecan nut shells (PES) were obtained mechanically in the manual cracking of nuts obtained from the Just-And Andrzej Błachowicz company (Poland). The country of origin of both nuts is the USA. Both nut grades were ground using a centrifugal Retsch ZM 200 knife mill in cryogenic conditions and then fractionated using 800 µm sieve.

2.1.2. Sample preparation

The rotomolding processing was performed by two routes, depending on the pre-processing steps. In the first case (named physical mixing and assigned as x1), the polymer pellets were ground in a high-speed mill Retsch ZM 200 at 8,000 rpm. The fillers were introduced at 2, 5, 10 and 15 wt% and mixed with the polymer powder; the blends were then dried at 70 °C for 24 h before rotational molding. 100 g of such premixes were introduced into the mold (180×60×60 mm), made of 2 mm-thick steel. The rotational molding was performed in a lab-scale single-arm shuttle rotational molding machine REMO GRAF (Poznan, Poland) [20], with rotation speeds of 10 and 8 rpm (horizontal and vertical axes, respectively). The heating chamber was settled to 230 °C, measuring a maximum of 200 °C in the spindle axis with a K-type thermocouple. The process inside the heating chamber lasted for 25 min, after which the mold was cooled with forced air flow for 15 min. The second method, i.e. melt mixing (x2), consisted of the preliminary blend preparation by an extrusion process. The compounding process was realized by a twin-screw co-rotating extruder Zamak 16/40 EHD, at 180 °C as maximum temperature, with a rotational speed of the screws of 100 rpm. The extrudates were cooled down with forced air before pelletizing. Pellets were ground in the high-speed mill Retsch ZM 200 in cryogenic

conditions at a knife rotational speed of 8,000 rpm. The prepared composite powders were processed by RM, using the same conditions as the material prepared by physical mixing (x1).

2.1.3. Methods

The chemical composition of nut shells, i.e., holocellulose, cellulose, lignin, mineral substances, and extractives, was analyzed using extraction methods following the procedures described in [21].

For both fillers, the standard Soxhlet procedure was used to determine the amount of oil. The oil content in organic waste fillers was assessed using the Büchi Universal Extraction System B-811, operating with petroleum ether as a solvent and a total extraction time of 150 min.

The DPPH free radical scavenging assay assessed the antioxidant properties of the used fillers. Samples of 1 g of each filler type were extracted in 100 ml of methanol for 30 min using a magnetic stirrer operating at 300 rpm at room temperature to obtain the required extracts for testing. Then, the filtered extracts were diluted to the concentration of 1 g/l. The antioxidant activity can be specified because of a stable organic nitrogen radical in 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH); its solution in alcohol has a violet color, which fades in the presence of the antioxidant. The UV-VIS spectrophotometer UviLine 9400 was used for analysis according to the procedure described in [10].

The particle size distribution of fillers was characterized using a laser particle sizer Fritsch ANALYSETTE 22 apparatus operating in the range of 0.08–2000 μm .

Rheological investigations were carried out using an Anton Paar MCR 301 rotational rheometer, with 25 mm diameter parallel plates and a 1.5 mm gap under the oscillatory mode. The experiments were conducted at 200°C. The angular frequency used during the studies was 0.05-500 rad/s with a strain of 1% (in the LVE range).

The oxidation induction time (OIT) of analyzed materials was determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The 5 ± 0.2 mg samples were placed in aluminum crucibles with pierced lids. They were heated from 20 to 190 °C with a heating rate of 20 °C/min in nitrogen, then kept at 190 °C for 5 min in nitrogen, and then the gas was switched to oxygen, and the time required for sample oxidation was measured. The measurements were conducted using a Netzsch 204 F1 Phoenix apparatus.

Tensile testing was used to study the elastic modulus, elongation at break, and tensile strength. The tensile tests were performed per ISO 527 standard with the Zwick/Roell Z020 model 5101 universal testing machine. The crosshead speed was set at 10 mm/min.

The impact strength was evaluated using the Dynstat method as in DIN 53435 standard on unnotched samples with dimensions of 4x10x15mm. A Dys-e 8421 apparatus with a 0.98 J hammer was used.

The composite samples were examined using measuring X-ray tomography, model v|tome|x s240 (Waygate Technologies / GE Sensing & Inspection Technologies GmbH). Micro-computed tomography (μCT) was used to evaluate the porosity in the rotomolded samples. Following scanning, parameters were used during the measurements - microfocus x-ray tube (voltage 150 kV/current 200 μA); the exposure time for one picture was 150 ms, and the voxel size was 123 μm .

3. Results and discussion

The results of the analysis of the chemical composition of plant-based fillers, along with their antioxidant activity, are summarized in Table 1 (all results of chemical compositions are given on a dry mass basis). PS is characterized by a lower lignin content compared to PES. The results are consistent with the literature data for this biomass group [22,23]. As shown in the literature [23,24], lignin, a compound rich in phenolic groups, has significant antioxidant activity. The results show a significantly higher PES antioxidant activity than PS. Analyzes showed four times greater inhibition ability and over 5 times greater value of Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC), which measures the antioxidant capacity of a given substance compared to the standard Trolox. This effect may probably be due to the increased content of oil, which contains low-molecular-weight active compounds.

Analysis of the particle size of the materials used showed different characteristics for fillers and polymer powder (Fig. 1). In the case of fillers, a bimodal particle size distribution was observed, with a dominant share of the fraction below 100 μm for PES and a more uniform distribution for PS. In both cases, the maximum particle size did not exceed 800 μm , which results from the cutting system used in the mill. In the case of polyethylene, the particle size distribution is much narrower and ranges from 20 to 1200 μm , with the dominant share of fractions in the range of 300-800 μm . The differences in particle size

may be related to a different chemical structure, including an increased cellulose content in the case of PS, resulting in more significant higher filler fractions [25].

Table 1. Chemical composition and results of antioxidant activity of PS and PES fillers.

Parameter	Unit	PS	PES
<i>Chemical composition</i>			
Holocellulose	[%]	88.26	75.88
Cellulose	[%]	32.69	27.92
Lignin	[%]	29.27	44.57
Mineral substances	[%]	0.2	1.67
Extractives	[%]	1.07	0.87
Oil	[%]	1.44	3.26
<i>Antioxidant activity</i>			
Inhibition	[%]	20.9 ± 2.1	88.4 ± 0.5
TAEC	[mg/g dry mass]	26.2 ± 3.8	148.3 ± 0.9

Figure 1. Particle size distribution of ground plant-based fillers and polymeric powder.

Complex viscosity curves made for samples taken from RM-products formed by one- and two-step processing procedures and made of HDPE and HDPE-PS/PES composites are presented in Fig. 2. The expected effect of introducing lignocellulosic fillers into the polymeric matrix is an increase in the viscosity [26]. In a considered case, using two varieties of fillers resulted in the opposite effect. Taking into account the results of our previous research related to the use of waste of plant origin with a high oil content (linseed cake) [27,28], the plasticizing effect resulting from the migration of oil from the filler during the technological process at elevated temperature, a gradual reduction in the viscosity of composites in the molten state is justified. At the same time, opposing effects of increasing viscosity caused by the presence of the HDPE-dispersed fraction and the plasticizing effect of reducing viscosity are observed. When using relatively low concentrations of fillers with a small fraction, the dominant phenomenon turned out to be the influence of oil. The presence of the polymeric bulk filler is evidenced by the gradual inflection of the curves in the range of small values of angular frequencies, observed in the case of concentrations of 10 and 15 wt%, which is related to hindering aggregated structures of rigid filler particles dispersed in polymeric bulk. Different rheological behaviors of composites with varying nutshells as fillers can be observed. In the case of composites containing PS, the lowest concentration of filler did not cause practically any changes in the relative viscosity curve of the reference material. However, a noticeably lower viscosity can be noted for the composite containing 2 wt% of PES. This effect is lower for melt processed series. It may be related to the better dispersed, smaller filler in HDPE. The significant reduction in viscosity in the case of PES-filled composites may result from, on the one hand, the higher oil content in the filler and its lower viscosity compared to pistachio oil [29,30].

Figure 2. Complex viscosity curves of HDPE and HDPE-PS/PES composites.

Table 2 lists the mechanical properties determined in the static tensile test (elastic modulus - E , tensile strength - R_m), impact strength (a_k), and porosity determined by μ CT. Introducing fillers into the polyethylene structure resulted in a gradual decrease in the elastic modulus and an increasing share of fillers. Reinforcing the effect of the presence of rigid filler structures in the PE matrix has been suppressed by two phenomena. The first is the plasticizing effect resulting in the oil migration from the filler, as described in [27]; the reduction in stiffness can also be associated with the increasing porosity of the composite. While nut shells were already introduced into the PE [31], causing an increase in stiffness, in the case of the RM, the much longer exposure time to elevated temperature during the technological cycle probably resulted in an intensification of the oil migration process into the polymer. In the case of all series produced with the two-step method (x2), the values of both elastic modulus and tensile strength are higher than for one-step processing (x1). This is related to the much lower porosity due to the use of regulated polymer filler particles dispersed in composite powder, as well as to the better dispersion of the filler in the matrix. Composites containing PES were characterized by increased porosity compared to the PS-filled series, resulting in worse mechanical properties. An agglomerated finely dispersed filler (PES) structure cannot be ruled out, as it accumulates stresses during loads. Powder fillers with regular shapes and limited relative adhesion of the polymer form micro notches, causing stress accumulation [32], mainly observed in dynamic loads. The impact strength values were significantly reduced due to the addition of both fillers. A more significant decrease in a_k was observed for PES composites. While a favorable melt-processing effect was observed in the case of PS-filled composites, the a_k values for the PES series were lower for most concentrations than for the composites formed using the physical mixing procedure.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of rotomolded HDPE and its' composites.

Material	E [MPa]	R_m [MPa]	a_K [kJ/m ²]	Porosity [%]
PE x1	1140 (45)	22.8 (0.7)	16.5 (1.8)	0.01
PE x2	1160 (57)	25.8 (0.9)	16.0 (2.9)	0.04
2PS x1	1040 (60)	20.7 (1.8)	7.13 (1.5)	2.83
2PS x2	1200 (24)	24.7 (0.9)	22.1 (5.8)	0.05
5PS x1	1090 (40)	19.5 (1.1)	4.6 (0.9)	3.99
5PS x2	1150 (46)	21.9 (1.5)	7.7 (1.4)	0.49
10PS x1	1020 (44)	14.8 (0.9)	3.5 (0.7)	6.39
10PS x2	1200 (27)	20 (0.8)	5.8 (2.1)	1.98
15PS x1	948 (36)	11.8 (0.8)	3.5 (0.8)	10.04
15PS x2	1150 (20)	15.1 (0.4)	3.3 (1.1)	7.97
2PES x1	1040 (29)	20.7 (0.4)	9.2 (1.8)	3.24
2PES x2	1100 (72)	23 (1.46)	9.4 (2.2)	0.39
5PES x1	897 (27)	15.7 (0.8)	6.4 (1.1)	7.05
5PES x2	1010 (21)	21.9 (0.9)	6.0 (1.0)	1.35
10PES x1	816 (15)	11.9 (0.6)	4.6 (0.7)	11.79
10PES x2	949 (50)	16.9 (0.9)	3.7 (0.8)	8.59
15PES x1	662 (53)	8.4 (0.8)	3.4 (0.7)	15.36
15PES x2	915 (72)	15.1 (0.7)	3.6 (0.4)	9.4

Table 3 presents the OIT values for polyethylene and composites formed in one- and two-step processing. Based on the change in the OIT value recorded for pure PE, it can be concluded that the process and the associated exposure to oxidizing conditions resulted in a decrease in the thermo-oxidative resistance of the polymer. This can be attributed to the formation of free radicals due to the extrusion process in the presence of high shear forces. The introduction of both fillers increased OIT compared to unfilled HDPE. More favorable results were measured for PES-filled composites. Taking into account the determined TAEC values, this effect was expected. The reduction in the OIT value in the case of composites subjected to two-stage preparation is related to the consumption of antioxidant compounds during extrusion. It should be emphasized that the resistance to melt oxidation was increased in the case of both nut varieties used.

Table 2. Oxygen induction time.

Filler amount wt%	Oxygen Induction Tim (OIT) [min]			
	<i>PS x1</i>	<i>PES x1</i>	<i>PS x2</i>	<i>PES x2</i>
0	69.2		16.4	
2	81.2	100.4	54.7	57.3
5	85.8	100.8	60.0	65.8
10	94.4	105.7	71.2	77.2
15	96.8	110.9	85.4	88.9

4. Conclusions

The completed tests allowed to successfully obtain composites in the RM process using two varieties of nut shells. It has been shown that it is possible to get a simultaneous interaction of the oil contained in the plant-originated filler as a plasticizer and stabilizer, increasing the resistance of the composite to thermooxidation. The use of a two-stage composite processing method, including initial homogenization of the composition using twin-screw co-rotating extrusion before pulverization, allowed for improvement in processability (limited porosity) and mechanical properties (higher tensile and impact strength) of rotomolded products compared to those made with the one-step procedure (physically mixed powdered polymer and fillers). Simultaneously, the oxidation resistance assessed by oxygen induction time (OIT-DSC) has been significantly improved after adding plant-based fillers; however, it reduced

in the case of melt-mixed composites. The PES-containing composites showed significantly higher oxidation resistance than the PS-filled series. It was found that a certain amount of antioxidants was consumed during melt-processing and rotomolding in the oxidative atmosphere, suppressing polyethylene process degradation, as a result of which the polymer was stabilized, but the number of active compounds in the final product was limited.

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References

- [1] J. L. Throne and M. -S. Sohn, Characterization of rotational molding grade polyethylene powders, *Advances in Polymer Technology*, 9:181–192, 1989.
- [2] K. O. Ogila, M. Shao, W. Yang and J. Tan, Rotational molding: A review of the models and materials, *Express Polymer Letters*, 11:778–798, 2017.
- [3] M. A. Rao and J. L. Throne, Principles of rotational molding, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 12(4):237–264, 1972.
- [4] K. Głogowska, F. Longwic and K. Ludziak, Effect of mould speed on selected properties of moulded parts and energy consumption in rotational moulding, *Bulletin of the Polish Academy of Sciences Technical Sciences*, 70(5):143106–143106, 2022.
- [5] A. Vignali, R. Utzeri, M. Canetti and F. Bertini, Crystallization Behavior of Poly(ϵ -Caprolactone)-Hollow Glass Microspheres Composites for Rotational Molding Technology, *Polymers*, 14(20):4326, 2022.
- [6] Z. Ortega, M. D. Monzón, A. N. Benítez, M. Kearns, M. McCourt and P. R. Hornsby, Banana and Abaca Fiber-Reinforced Plastic Composites Obtained by Rotational Molding Process, *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, 28(8):879–883, 2013.
- [7] R. H. López-Bañuelos, F. J. Moscoso, P. Ortega-Gudiño, E. Mendizabal, D. Rodrigue and R. González-Núñez, Rotational molding of polyethylene composites based on agave fibers, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 52(12):2489–2497, 2012.
- [8] J. Aniśko, D. Bartczak and M. Barczewski, Limitations of Short Basalt Fibers Use as an Effective Reinforcement of Polyethylene Composites in Rotational Molding Technology, *Advances in Science and Technology Research Journal*, 17(3):110–123, 2023.
- [9] A. Arribasplata-Seguín, R. Quispe-Dominguez, W. Tupia-Anticona and J. Acosta-Sullcahuamán, Rotational molding parameters of wood-plastic composite materials made of recycled high density polyethylene and wood particles, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 217:108876, 2021.
- [10] J. Aniśko, M. Barczewski, A. Piasecki, K. Skórczewska, J. Szulc and M. Szostak, The Relationship between a Rotational Molding Processing Procedure and the Structure and Properties of Biobased Polyethylene Composites Filled with Expanded Vermiculite, *Materials*, 15(17):5903, 2022.
- [11] S. Díaz, Z. Ortega, M. McCourt, M.P. Kearns and A.N. Benítez, Recycling of polymeric fraction of cable waste by rotational moulding, *Waste Management*, 76:199–206, 2018.
- [12] Z. Ortega, L. Suárez, J. Kelly-Walley and M. McCourt, Mechanical properties of rotomolded parts with abaca fiber: effect of manufacturing with 1, 2 or 3 layers, *Composites Theory and Practice*, 23(3):158–166, 2023.
- [13] Z. Ortega, P. Douglas, P. R. Hanna, J. Kelly-Walley and M. McCourt, Influence of mold pressurization on cycle time in rotational molding composites with welded ignimbrite as loading, *Composites Communications*, 45:101797, 2024.
- [14] Z. Ortega, L. Suárez, J. Kelly-Walley, P. R. Hanna, M. McCourt and B. Millar, Use of Pressure in Rotational Molding to Reduce Cycle Times: Comparison of the Thermomechanical Behavior of Rotomolded Reed/Polyethylene Composites, *Journal of Composites Science*, 8(1):17, 2024.
- [15] A. S. M. Bashir and Y. Manusamy, Recent Developments in Biocomposites Reinforced with Natural Biofillers from Food Waste, *Polymer-Plastics Technology and Engineering* 54(1):87–99, 2015.

- [16] J. Aniśko and M. Barczewski, Uniaxial Rotational Molding of Bio-Based Low-Density Polyethylene Filled with Black Tea Waste, *Materials*, 16(10):3641, 2023.
- [17] M. I. Baumer, J. L. Leite and D. Becker, Influence of calcium carbonate and slip agent addition on linear medium density polyethylene processed by rotational molding, *Materials Research*, 17(1):130–137, 2013.
- [18] O. Pınar, F. E. Koc, M. B. Alanalp, N. Sivri, A. Ezdesir and A. Durmus, Utilization of Silybum marianum extract as a high-performance natural antioxidant for polyethylene, *Journal of Materials Science*, 59:3725–3741, 2024.
- [19] M. Barczewski, Z. Ortega, P. Piaskowski, J. Aniśko, P. Kosmela and J. Szulc, A case study on the rotomolding behavior of black tea waste and bio-based high-density polyethylene composites: Do active compounds in the filler degrade during processing?, *Composites Part C: Open Access*, 13:100437, 2024.
- [20] M. Barczewski, M. Szostak, D. Nowak and A. Piasecki, Effect of wood flour addition and modification of its surface on the properties of rotationally molded polypropylene composites, *Polimery*, 63(11-12):772–784, 2018.
- [21] M. Herkowiak, A. Osuch, E. Osuch, B. Waliszewska and G. Zając, Analysis of the Possibility of Management of Curly-Leaf Pondweed for Energetic Purposes, *Energies*, 14(17):5477, 2021.
- [22] J. B. Engel, M. Mac Ginity, C. L. Luchese, I. C. Tessaro and J. C. Spada, Reuse of Different Agroindustrial Wastes: Pinhão and Pecan Nutshells Incorporated into Biocomposites Using Thermocompression, *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 28:1431–1440, 2020.
- [23] M. Čolnik, M. Irgolič, A. Perva and M. Škerget, The Conversion of Pistachio and Walnut Shell Waste into Valuable Components with Subcritical Water, *Processes*, 12(1):195, 2024.
- [24] C. E. Okonkwo, S. Z. Hussain, H. Onyeaka, A. A. Adeyanju, C. O. Nwonuma, A. A. Bashir, A. Farooq, C. Zhou and T. D. Shittu, Lignin polyphenol: From biomass to innovative food applications, and influence on gut microflora, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 206:117696, 2023.
- [25] F. S. P. P. Neto, E. A. de Lucca and F. Masarin, Particle Size Influence on the Chemical Composition from Waste Eucalyptus in the Processing for Industrial Production of Cellulose Pulp, *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, 50:337–342, 2016.
- [26] V. Mazzanti and F. Mollica, A Review of Wood Polymer Composites Rheology and Its Implications for Processing, *Polymers*, 12(10):2304, 2020.
- [27] M. Barczewski, O. Mysiukiewicz and A. Kloziński, Complex modification effect of linseed cake as an agricultural waste filler used in high density polyethylene composites, *Iranian Polymer Journal*, 27:677–688, 2018.
- [28] M. Barczewski, O. Mysiukiewicz, J. Szulc and A. Kloziński, Poly(lactic acid) green composites filled with linseed cake as an agricultural waste filler. Influence of oil content within the filler on the rheological behavior, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 136(24):47651, 2019.
- [29] A. Rabadán, J. E. Pardo, R. Gómez, A. Alvarruiz and M. Álvarez-Ortí, Usefulness of physical parameters for pistachio cultivar differentiation, *Scientia Horticulturae*, 222:7–11, 2017.
- [30] K. Okafor, M. Danjaji and M. Figura, Viscosity Modeling and Flow Properties of Non-Edible Oils as Feed- Stocks in Biodiesel Production, *International Journal of Earth & Environmental Sciences*, 4:162, 2019.
- [31] K. Salasinska and J. Ryszkowska, The effect of filler chemical constitution and morphological properties on the mechanical properties of natural fiber composites, *Composite Interfaces*, 22(1):39–50, 2015.
- [32] V. Švehlová and E. Polouček, About the influence of filler particle size on toughness of filled polypropylene, *Die Angewandte Makromolekulare Chemie*, 153(1):197–200, 1987.